

Plankton Diversity in Freshwater Lake Ambona Near Umarkhed, MS, India

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Manuscript Details

Available online on <https://www.irjse.in>
ISSN: 2322-0015

Cite this article as:

Bhojar VV. Plankton Diversity in Freshwater Lake Ambona Near Umarkhed, MS, India, *Int. Res. Journal of Science & Engineering*, 2024, Special Issue A15: 41-44.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14239669>

Article published in Special issue of International Conference on International Conference on Global Sustainable Global Sustainable Development (ICGSD-2024) Bangkok, Thailand" Jointly organized by Digambarrao Bindu College, Bhokar, Nanded, MS, India, Shri. Shivaji Science College Amravati, MS, India & Asian Foundation for Scientific Research and Innovation (AFSRI) on date 6th & 7th June, 2024

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Abstract

The water quality monitoring is usually done by assessment of physico-chemical parameters or analyzing the plankton and micro invertebrates. Eutrophication is the process in which the water bodies receive extra nutrients that stimulate algal growth. Algal growth covers the water body and sunlight can't enter to the bottom, so that organisms don't get oxygen and sunlight. Nutrients that cause these algal blooms can come from a variety of sources: fertilizer sprayings, agricultural runoff, animal waste, industrial wastes etc. Ambona Lake is situated 3 km away from Umarkhed city. The water from this lake is used for agriculture purpose, drinking, washing, and fishery management. During the study period Jan 2017 to Dec. 2017, samples were collected monthly from 7 to 9 am and analyzed, for the physico-chemical parameters, study of phytoplankton and zooplanktons.

Keywords: Phytoplankton, Zooplankton, Physico-chemical Parameters, Ambona Lake.

Introduction

Every living organism depends on other organism for food. This feeding cycle is called as a food chain. The base of food chain is primary productivity that is green plants in depend upon zooplanktons for energy, aquatic ecosystem the base of food chain is phytoplankton. Zooplanktons depend on phytoplankton for their food and large organisms. Study on Ecology of zooplankton population from various parts of India is available from the investigation of Sreenivasan [1],

Michael [2], Mathivanan et al. [3] and Kuadri and Kanamadi [4]. Chattopadhyay and Banerjee [5,6], worked on seasonal variations of plankton and their relationship with physico-chemical parameters of water in Krishna Sayer Lake, Burdwan, West Bengal.

Methodology

The physico-Chemical parameters of waters studied were water temperature, transparency, turbidity, pH, Dissolved oxygen, alkalinity, free CO₂, nitrogen and chloride. The analysis of water samples was done according to APHA [7]. The chemical parameters except pH (Units) were expressed in mg/lit. Filtered samples were fixed and preserved by adding Lugol's Iodine for phytoplankton and 4% formalin for the zooplanktons.

Identification of phytoplankton was done with the help of keys of APHA and Kodarkar's methodology. For zooplankton identification, the methods described by Sehgal [8], Battish [9], Dhanapathi [10] was used.

Results and Discussion

The assessment and monitoring of various physical and chemical and biological parameter represent the condition of water body. The limits of parameters or presence and absence of some species show that the lake is moving towards eutrophication. The investigations of the parameters, indicate high pH values. This may be due to the natural causes, and the agricultural runoff from the catchment.

Table 1: Maximum and minimum values of various physico-chemical parameters

JAN 2022-DEC 2023	MEAN	SD	SE	CV	RANGE	MAX.	MIN.
WT	28.100	3.526	1.018	7.969		33.000	22.500
TURBIDITY	14.583	4.166	1.203	3.501		22.000	6.000
TRANSAP.	51.500	13.595	3.924	3.788		79.000	36.000
PH	7.323	0.235	0.068	31.130		7.800	7.050
DO (MG/L)	6.483	1.583	0.457	4.095		9.200	3.500
CO2 (MG/L)	0.591	0.524	0.151	1.128		1.500	0.000
ALK. (MG/L)	61.750	17.126	4.944	3.606		97.000	40.000
CHLOR. (MG/L)	63.167	10.769	3.109	5.866		81.000	48.000
NIT. (MG/L)	0.431	0.072	0.021	6.012		0.510	0.300
CHLOROPHYCEAE	72.417	19.086	5.510	3.794		102.000	41.000
BACILLARIOPHYCEAE	29.333	9.736	2.811	3.013		50.000	14.000
CYANOPHYCEAE	18.333	4.008	1.157	4.575		23.000	12.000
EUGLENOPHYCEAE	9.083	1.505	0.434	6.035		12.000	6.000
TOTAL.PHY. PLANKTON	129.167	27.584	7.963	4.683		165.000	78.000
ROTIFERA	10.833	2.918	0.842	3.712		15.000	5.000
COPEPODA	7.500	3.000	0.866	2.500		12.000	2.000
CLADOCERA	6.750	2.832	0.818	2.383		11.000	2.000
OSTRACODA	4.750	2.454	0.708	1.936		8.000	1.000

Thus, the analysis of various parameters showed high percentage of *Microcystis* and *Navicula* sp. Also, the phytoplankton analysis in lake reveals the dominance of Chlorophyceae members, which indicate that lake is organically polluted. The seasonal abundance of phytoplankton in the present investigations show fall in monsoon followed by rise in post monsoon and more in spring followed by little fluctuations in summer. This may be due to grazing pressure exerted by zooplanktons as well as fish. Ambona Lake phytoplankton also shows a high density of Chlorophyceae members dominated by *spirogyra* sp., *Pediastrum* sp., and *Euglena* sp. These observations are similar with those of Chaturvedi *et al.* [11,12-15]. Presence of *Microcystis* and *Anabaena*, *Euglena* sp. and high alkalinity indicates the trend of the water body towards eutrophication. Similar genera were recorded in the present investigation.

Among zooplanktons Rotifers was the dominant group. Zooplanktons were higher in winter may be due to favorable temperature and availability of high amount of nutrients in the form of primary producers. Among the zooplanktons three species *Cyclopes*, *moniodaphnia*, *branchionus*, *bosmania* and *rotararia* are pollution indicator species which are found in eutrophic waters [16-17].

The overall opinion about the lake is that the temperature, alkalinity, dissolved oxygen, carbon dioxide, chlorides and nitrates these all factors affects the plankton of biodiversity of the Ambona Lake. The amount of water in the lake has as impact on the wetland biodiversity of lake and at present the lake is eutrophic. It needs protection from animal activities as well as agricultural runoff to stop further eutrophication and proper bioremediation practices can save the lake.

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Conflicts of interest: The authors stated that no conflicts of interest.

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